

Stig2Health: Stigma-directed services to improve ‘linkage to care’ for people living with HIV in rural Tanzania: study protocol for a nested pre-post implementation study within the Kilombero and Ulanga Antiretroviral Cohort

End of Study Questionnaire

1	Screening Question: Since you have been diagnosed with HIV, have you ever joined a group therapy session provided by our clinic (CDCI or OSC)?	Toka ugundulike na VVU umewahi kujiunga na kikundi cha majadiliano hapa kliniki ya mama, baba na mtoto (OSC)/ kliniki ya watu wazima (CDCI/Adult clinic)?
2	From a scale of 0 to 10 (0= Not likely, 10= Very likely), how likely are you to recommend group therapy sessions to other people living with HIV?	Je, Kwa kiwango gani kati ya 0 mpaka 10 ungependekeza kikundi cha majadiliano kwa watu wengine wanaoishi na VVU? (0 ikiwa sipendekezi kabisa na 10 ikiwa napendekeza sana)
3	Screening Question: Since you have been diagnosed with HIV, did you watch the HIV video provided by the clinic?	Toka ugundulike kuwa na VVU umeangalia video kuhusu VVU hapa kliniki?
4	From a scale of 0 to 10 (0= Not likely, 10= Very likely), how likely are you to recommend the HIV video to patients that are newly diagnosed with HIV?	Je, Kwa kiwango gani kati ya 0 mpaka 10 ungependekeza video hiyo ya VVU kwa watu walio gundulika wanaoishi na VVU? (0 ikiwa sipendekezi kabisa na 10 ikiwa napendekeza sana)
5	Screening Question: Since you have been diagnosed with HIV, did you receive the phone call reminder(s) provided by the counselors?	Toka ugundulike kuwa na VVU, ulipokea simu kutoka kwa mshauri kukukumbusha juu ya mahudhurio yako kliniki
6	From a scale of 0 to 10 (0= Not likely, 10= Very likely), how likely are you to recommend phone call reminder(s) to patients that are newly diagnosed with HIV?	Je, Kwa kiwango gani kati ya 0 mpaka 10 ungependekeza huduma hii ya kupigiwa simu kwa watu waliogundulika wanaoishi na VVU? (0 ikiwa sipendekezi kabisa na 10 ikiwa napendekeza sana)
7	Screening Question: Since you have been diagnosed with HIV, did you receive the counselling by a counselor living with HIV?	Toka ugundulike kuwa na VVU, umepokea ushauri nasihitoka kwa mshauri anayeishi na VVU?
8	From a scale of 0 to 10 (0= Not likely, 10= Very likely), how likely are you to recommend counselling by a counselor living with HIV to other people that are newly diagnosed with HIV?	Je, Kwa kiwango gani kati ya 0 mpaka 10 ungependekeza kupata ushauri nasaha kutoka kwa mshauri anayeishi na VVU kwa watu wengine waliogundulika wanaoishi na VVU? (0 ikiwa sipendekezi kabisa na 10 ikiwa napendekeza sana)
9	From a scale of 0 to 10 (0= Not likely, 10= Very likely), how likely are you to recommend the Depression and Stigma assessment to other people that are living with HIV?	Je, Kwa kiwango gani kati ya 0 mpaka 10 ungependekeza tadhmini ya sonona na unyanyapaa kwa watu wengine wanaoishi na VVU? (0 ikiwa sipendekezi kabisa na 10 ikiwa napendekeza sana)
10	Was the length of this questionnaire appropriate?	Urefu wa dodosa hii ulikua unafaa?
11	Was the language used to ask the questions easy and simple to understand?	Je, lugha iliyotumika kuulizia maswali ilikua rahisi na ya kueleweka?
12	Were there any question in the questionnaire that were not appropriate or that you did not feel comfortable to answer them?	Je, kwenye dodosa kulikuemo maswali ambayo yalikuwafanya usiwe huru kujibu au haya kukufaa?